

UNDERSTANDING DERIVATIVES: ASSOCIATED RISKS AND POTENTIAL REWARDS

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Abstract. *The primary objective of this article is to provide a comprehensive understanding of derivatives, highlighting their significance in financial markets and the diverse strategies utilized to mitigate risks for both businesses and investors. In addition, the article will dive into the history of its evolution and possible hazards linked to these complex financial instruments.*

Key words: *financial derivatives, Code of Hammurabi, Aristotle's Politics, Osaka rice exchange, futures contract, forward contract, option, swap, hedging, risk management, hedger, arbitrageur, speculator, commodity risk, exchange rate risk, credit risk, credit default swap.*

ПОНИМАНИЕ ПРОИЗВОДНЫХ ФИНАНСОВ: СВЯЗАННЫЕ РИСКИ И ПОТЕНЦИАЛЬНЫЕ НАГРАДЫ

Аннотация. *Основная цель этой статьи — дать всестороннее представление о деривативах, подчеркнув их значение на финансовых рынках и разнообразные стратегии, используемые для снижения рисков как для бизнеса, так и для инвесторов. Кроме того, в статье будет рассмотрена история его развития и возможные опасности, связанные с этими сложными финансовыми инструментами.*

Ключевые слова: *производные финансовые инструменты, Кодекс Хаммурапи, Политика Аристотеля, Осацкая рисовая биржа, фьючерсный контракт, форвардный контракт, опцион, своп, хеджирование, управление рисками, хеджер, арбитражер, спекулянт, товарный риск, валютный риск, кредитный риск, кредитно-дефолтный своп.*

INTRODUCTION

Financial derivatives are a classification of financial instruments that derive their value from an underlying asset or a collection of assets. These instruments cover a broad spectrum of financial products that serve various purposes and cater to diverse needs in the market.

Financial derivatives provide protection against potential losses and are utilized as a powerful tool to effectively handle and mitigate risks, while also allowing individuals and entities to participate in speculation activities related to price fluctuations.

Given the interdependent nature of the modern global economy, financial derivatives assume a pivotal role in facilitating the operation of financial markets. In the finance sector, possessing a profound understanding of financial derivatives is of utmost significance, particularly for individuals aspiring to embark on investment or pursue a professional path in this domain.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Historical background

First derivatives can be traced back to ancient Mesopotamia nearly 3,800 years ago. Their most primitive form was mentioned in the Code of Hammurabi ^[1], one of the earliest written legal

documents in the history of human civilization. The code consisted of a comprehensive set of 282 laws that established guidelines for conducting commercial activities and stipulated penalties and sanctions to ensure justice. The significance of the code during that era can be seen through its role in providing a legal structure for business dealings, governing the behavior of merchants and establishing guidelines for settling conflicts between traders ^[2]^[3].

The 48th law of the code proclaimed that “If any one owe a debt for a loan, and a storm prostrates the grain, or the harvest fail, or the grain does not grow for lack of water; in that year he need not give his creditor any grain, he washes his debt-tablet in water and pays no rent for the year” ^[4].

It appears that during that time, a regular farmer would have a loan on his land and was obligated to make annual interest payments in the form of grain. In the event of crop failure, the farmer had the option to forgo interest payments and the lender had no alternative but to accept it. Experts in the field of derivatives would classify this agreement as a put option ^[4].

A subsequent indication of derivatives in historical records can be traced back to Aristotle’s *Politics*. Aristotle mentions Thales, a philosopher and mathematician from Miletus, who made a remarkable prediction about an abundant olive harvest by carefully observing the winter sky. Thales took advantage of this by engaging in negotiations with the owners of the olive presses, in order to secure the right, but not the obligation, of renting all of the olive presses in the region for the upcoming autumn season. As predicted, the harvest turned out to be bountiful, which led to an increase in demand for the use of olive presses. Today, professionals would categorize this particular financial instrument as a call option ^[4].

The earliest documented evidence of a structured marketplace for exchanging derivatives can be traced back to the 17th century in Osaka. During this time, Osaka became the primary trading center for rice in Japan. Rice played a significant role in the economy, with shipments coming from all over the country and being stored in Osaka. The rice was then sold through auctions, and after a deal was made, sellers would issue a certificate of title for the rice in exchange for money. Merchants had the option to hold onto the bills or sell them, hoping to make a quick profit within a specific timeframe preceding the delivery of rice. However, as the market evolved, the delivery dates were extended. The rice bills represented the right to receive a predetermined quantity of rice at a future date but at the current price, making them comparable to modern-day forward contracts ^[1].

Categorization of financial derivatives

In the present day, investors intending to acquire a derivative contract may find themselves overwhelmed by the extensive array of options available to them. There exist hundreds of different types of derivative instruments, making it initially appear intimidating and perplexing. Nonetheless, such variations of derivative instruments can ultimately be categorized into one of four distinct groups.

Forward contracts

Forward contracts are considered to be the most basic form of derivatives in the financial market. In essence, a forward contract can be defined as a contractual arrangement that involves the commitment to sell a certain item or asset at a predetermined time in the future. The specific value at which this exchange will occur is determined at the current time ^[5].

A forward contract is executed between two counterparties, without the involvement of an intermediary, thus amplifying the likelihood of counterparty credit risk. It is imperative to acknowledge that if these contracts need to be terminated prematurely, the terms may not be favorable, as both parties have only one option, which is to negotiate with the other party. The specifics of the forward contracts are confidential information for both parties involved, and there is no obligation to disclose this information to the general public [5].

Futures contracts

A futures contract shares numerous similarities with a forward contract. These similarities can be attributed to the fact that both contracts entail the obligation to sell a specific asset at a predetermined price at a later date. Nevertheless, futures contracts are specifically traded on the exchange platform, which implies the involvement of an intermediary in the transaction process [6].

These contracts are standardized, and the terms of the agreement are non-negotiable. Futures contracts are available in predetermined formats, sizes and expirations. Furthermore, due to their association with the exchange, these contracts abide by a daily settlement procedure, obligating any profits or losses incurred in a given day to be resolved on the same day. This practice aims to eliminate the potential counterparty credit risk commonly associated with such transactions [6].

Options

The third category of financial derivatives bear a significant difference in comparison with the preceding categories. In forward and futures contracts, both parties were contractually obliged to execute a certain action (buying or selling an underlying asset) on a predetermined date. When it comes to option contracts, one party assumes the obligation of buying or selling an asset, whereas the other party is given the freedom to choose whether to buy or sell. Consequently, the party making the choice is required to pay a premium for this privilege [6].

Swaps

Swaps are likely the most intricate financial instruments within the derivatives market. They allow individuals to exchange their cash flow streams. For instance, at a later time, one party may exchange an uncertain cash flow for a guaranteed one, with the most common scenario being the exchange of a fixed interest rate for a floating one. Parties may also choose to swap the underlying currency [5].

Swap contracts offer companies the advantage of mitigating various risks, including foreign exchange risks. Unlike exchange-traded contracts, swap contracts are typically conducted privately between two parties, usually with the involvement of investment bankers as intermediaries [5].

Importance of financial derivatives and their primary users

Derivatives are important as they can provide reassurance to individuals who find uncertainty unfavorable, such as a farmer who relies on weather conditions for their crops and profits. Although derivatives cannot alter the weather itself, they are capable of altering the financial consequences of a drought.

Apart from the weather, companies face the risk of fluctuations in commodity prices, exchange rates and interest rates. The prices of essential resources in the production cycle, such as

crude oil or copper, change on a daily basis, making future expenses and revenues unpredictable. Financial derivatives provide companies with the option to minimize their vulnerability to unforeseen fluctuations in the markets for essential commodities and raw materials [7].

There are three different types of traders in derivatives markets, each having their own interests, specific roles and strategies, unique market perspectives, different levels of financial risks and varying degrees of tolerance towards risks: hedgers, arbitrageurs and speculators [6].

Hedgers are individuals or organizations who participate in hedging transactions in order to reduce potential risks related to their business or investment endeavors. These risks may include being exposed to unpredictable commodity prices, fluctuating interest rates or unstable exchange rates [8].

Arbitrageurs are individuals or entities that implement an arbitrage approach with the intention of capitalizing on a disparity between a derivative and its underlying asset, which could include commodities, currencies, interest rates or securities. This disparity arises when there is a difference in value of the derivative and its underlying asset [9].

Speculators participate in speculative transactions with the intention of earning profits by leveraging market price fluctuations. Unlike hedging or arbitrage transactions, where investors aim to mitigate risks or exploit price disparities, speculators purposely assume opposing positions to these transactions [10].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The selection of the research methodology for this article was based on careful consideration of multiple factors. These factors encompassed the primary question of the study, the availability of analogous academic papers exploring the similar topic and the necessary data required for the research.

To obtain the required information, a secondary data collection method was adopted for the study. This specific method facilitated the swift collection of readily available materials and information from diverse sources on the internet. The abundance of previously conducted studies in this particular area contributed to the ease of accessing such data.

The author acknowledged the significance of employing a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches in analyzing the data, ultimately ensuring that the research outcomes are meaningful and robust.

ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Businesses and individual investors rely on financial derivatives as instruments to increase or decrease their exposure to three prevalent categories of risk, namely commodity risk, exchange rate risk and credit risk.

Exposure to commodity risk

A company that is required to purchase a particular commodity at a later date faces the potential danger of a sudden upsurge in the cost of that commodity. To mitigate this risk, the company may employ a widely used derivative instrument known as a futures contract. Such a contract assists the company in minimizing its vulnerability to fluctuations in the prices of the commodity in question.

When a company purchases a commodity futures contract, it commits to a specific price that it will pay for the acquisition of that commodity at a later point in time. Subsequently, the

individual who sells the contract is bound to deliver the specified commodity on a predetermined future date, adhering to the agreed-upon price. This future timeframe may span from several months to several years.

A case of JSC “Kvarts” could be deployed as an example to demonstrate the practical application of financial derivatives for hedging commodity risk. Established in 1975, JSC “Kvarts” is one of the leading companies in Central Asia that specializes in the production of colored, tinted and tempered glass, alongside glass jars and bottles. Company uses quartz sand as a main ingredient for the manufacturing of products and its profitability is significantly influenced by the fluctuations in the market value of this essential resource ^[11].

The average price for quartz sand in October 2023 stands at 276,545 sums per ton ^[12]. At this point, JSC “Kvarts” has the option to secure this October 2023 price or alternatively take a risk by speculating that prices might decrease in the future. However, if the company’s prediction proves to be inaccurate and the prices unexpectedly rise beyond 276,545 sums, it could potentially damage the company’s earnings or compel them to raise prices for their products.

JSC “Kvarts” mitigates commodity risk by acquiring a futures contract, thereby redirecting attention towards their core business of producing glass products, while alleviating concerns over fluctuating raw material prices. Conversely, the quartz sand producer secures a fixed price for their product by selling the futures, safeguarding against potential declines in market prices in the future.

Exposure to exchange rate risk

Exchange rate risk occurs when a company engages in international trade by either exporting or importing goods and services, and the value of its domestic currency fluctuates in relation to foreign currencies. To address and mitigate these risks, a company may employ forward contracts or currency options as effective mechanisms in safeguarding against potential unfavorable movements in exchange rates.

A currency option grants a business the choice, without imposing any obligation, to purchase or sell a specific currency at a later date, using a pre-defined exchange rate. On the other hand, the counterparty involved in this transaction assumes the obligation to either buy or sell the specified currency at a predetermined date and exchange rate. In return for undertaking this obligation, the counterparty receives a certain sum of money known as premium.

To illustrate the application of financial derivatives in mitigating foreign exchange rate risk, we can delve into the theoretical case of JSC “UzAuto Motors”, a state-owned automotive manufacturer in Uzbekistan. The company specializes in the production and distribution of passenger cars and ultra-small minibuses under the Chevrolet brand ^[13].

Semiconductors play a crucial role in the manufacturing process of automobiles, serving as one of the vital components. Every vehicle produced by the company incorporates a range of 100 to 300 various components that rely on semiconductors. These semiconductors are sourced from a network of 38 international suppliers, meeting the demand for 67 distinct components across the company’s entire product lineup ^[14].

After analyzing the fluctuations in the value of the Uzbek sum in comparison to major currencies such as the US dollar and Euro, we can observe that the value of the Uzbek sum depreciated significantly over the past years. As indicated in Figure 1, this decline in value exceeded fourfold between the period of 2016 and 2023 ^[15].

Figure 1. Exchange rate of the Uzbek sum against the US dollar and Euro, 2016-2023

If the value of the Uzbek sum continues to decrease in the future, it will lead to an increase in the cost of imported semiconductors, thus negatively impacting the profitability of the company. Therefore, using currency options or forward contracts would enable the company to secure the current exchange rates of the Uzbek sum and help it effectively manage and minimize the potential risks arising from exchange rate fluctuations.

Exposure to credit risk

Credit risk is the possibility that a company may default on its financial commitments. Investors become vulnerable to credit risk when they acquire a company's debt. In the event that a company fails to fulfill its debt obligations, credit default swaps (CDS) offer a protective measure to investors.

CDSs are financial derivatives that enable investors to safeguard themselves from the possibility of default on a specific debt instrument, such as a bond or loan. When a CDS is employed, the purchaser pays the seller a premium in return for insurance against default on the underlying debt. In case the borrower fails to repay, the seller of the CDS is obliged to reimburse the buyer a sum matching the value of the underlying debt instrument.

If an investor decides to purchase a bond issued by LLC "Artel Electronics" with the face value of 100 million sums^[16], but wants to minimize the potential credit risk associated with this bond, they can decide to buy a CDS. By doing so, the investor can protect themselves against the potential default of LLC "Artel Electronics" on their debt. In the unfortunate event that the company fails to repay the debt, the investor will be entitled to receive financial compensation amounting to the face value of the bond from the party that sold the CDS.

Risks of financial derivatives

In his annual letter addressed to Berkshire Hathaway shareholders in 2002, Warren Buffett warned investors about the issues inherent in the over-the-counter derivatives market. He stated that due to multiple flaws in the market's functioning, derivatives could be regarded as "financial weapons of mass destruction". Buffett's letter pointed out two particular vulnerabilities, namely an excessive exposure to the risk of one party failing to fulfill its financial obligations (bilateral credit risk) and insufficient collateral (margin) to offset potential losses^[17].

These problems became more apparent during the global financial crisis of 2008. Prior to the market collapse, American International Group, an insurance and finance corporation, held CDSs for investments related to mortgages. As a result of the subsequent housing bubble burst and the decline in mortgage values, the company incurred losses from its derivative positions and its financial health was severely damaged. Eventually, the company's substantial losses arising from its derivatives agreements became overwhelming, prompting the intervention of the government. Recognizing the potential devastating impact its insolvency could have on the financial system, the Federal Reserve responded by allocating a significant sum of capital, amounting to 85 billion US dollars.

Warren Buffett's predictions regarding the derivatives market were proven to be accurate as there was a significant economic disruption caused by extensive uncollateralized derivatives positions. In response to these concerns and the flaws highlighted by American International Group's failure, the Dodd-Frank Act was introduced to tackle the issues in the derivatives market.

CONCLUSION

The derivatives market serves as a platform where investors gather to trade risks related to financial markets. In today's interconnected global economy, characterized by varying risk profiles, derivatives play a crucial role in enabling businesses and investors to safeguard against sudden and significant changes in prices and adverse events.

Before the crisis, the derivatives market lacked a robust regulatory framework that effectively governed its operations. The absence of adequate regulations led to a surplus of bilateral credit risk, meaning that the parties involved in derivatives transactions faced a high level of potential default. Moreover, these transactions were not sufficiently collateralized, which means that there was insufficient security or guarantees provided to offset any potential losses.

As the process of regulating the derivatives market progresses, it is crucial for policymakers to focus on safeguarding this market as a means of risk management, rather than allowing it to become a potential source of risk.

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